

Flaxseed proteome as precursors of antioxidant peptides: an *in silico* study

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Highlights

- ❑ Matured flaxseed proteins are mostly globulins, oleosins, and conlinin.
- ❑ *In silico* digestion of flaxseed proteins gave peptides with antioxidant properties
- ❑ Plant proteases are excellent enzymes for releasing antioxidant peptides from flaxseed proteins.
- ❑ Antioxidant properties showed structural and physicochemical features important for antioxidation.

1: Background

For use in controlling oxidation both in food/cosmetic products and in human body systems, various antioxidant compounds and ingredients have been developed. With the growing consumer preference for “natural” sources and the demand for food/drug compatible, developing novel antioxidant peptides from food materials has become a major research endeavour at the interface of functional food and public health [1, 2, 3]. In this study, flaxseed was used due to their increasing reputation as a ‘superfood’ [4]. Bioinformatics tools allows for the prediction of the release of bioactive peptides, prior to confirmation by wet lab synthesis, thereby speeding up the discovery of peptides with desired properties, in this case antioxidant properties [5].

2: Objective

To utilize bioinformatics tools to investigate properties of 23 matured storage flaxseed proteins and *in silico* released antioxidant peptides with (9) proteolytic enzymes.

3: Methods

Screen proteome of matured flaxseed storage proteins (~23 proteins)

Matured proteins (48 days after anthesis) [6]

Database mining and *in silico* digestion with (9) proteolytic enzymes

Prediction and analysis of antioxidant peptides released

BIOPEP descriptors [7]:

Ae - frequency of release of fragments with given activity by selected enzymes;

W - relative frequency of release of fragments with given activity by selected enzymes

4: Results

Table 1: Physicochemical characteristics of Proteins

Characteristic	Oleosins	Globulins/Conlinin
GRAVY	0.03 - 0.34	-0.82 - 0.08
MW	15.4 - 20.5	19.01 - 60.52
pI	9.7 - 10.6	5.6 - 9.1
BI	0.47 - 0.99	0.98 - 2.68
Net-charge	3.27 - 6.52	- 10.44 - 6.54

Fig 2: Enzyme types and their hydrolytic performance

MW distribution of peptides

Fig 2: MW distribution of antioxidant peptides

Fig 3: Types of antioxidant peptides

Distribution of hydrophobicity

Fig 3: Distribution of hydrophobicity

5: Conclusion

- ❑ Matured flaxseed proteins are mostly globulins, oleosins, and conlinin.
- ❑ All peptides were non-toxic, and differed in water solubility profile
- ❑ Some abundant peptides were EL, IR, HL, and ADF, RHL, etc.
- ❑ Flaxseed proteome is a potential source of antioxidant peptides
- ❑ Plant proteases are most suitable for releasing these peptides

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7. References

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